

The air dried powdered aerial parts (leaves and stems) of *N. Stellata* Willd. was extracted successively with light petrol (b.p. 60-80°) and ethanol. The concentrated petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with benzene afforded a solid, crystallised from methanol, m.p. 135-36°. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test for sterol and was identified as β -sitosterol by comparative studies (m.m.p. co-ir and co-tlc) with an authentic sample and through the preparation of acetate, m.p. 127-28°.

The concentrated ethanolic extract on chromatography over silica gel and on elution with ethyl acetate furnished a solid crystallised from methanol in fine plates, $C_{17}H_{19}O_3N$ (M^+285), m.p. 220-22°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 250 (phenolic OH) and 3 400 cm^{-1} (NH); λ_{max} (EtOH) 281 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.80) and 254 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.68) similar to benzyloisoquinoline alkaloids³; mass spectrum is typical of benzyloisoquinoline type of alkaloids⁴, significant peaks m/e 285 (M^+), 178 and 163. From the study of these data as well as from the formation of dimethyl ether derivative, m.p. 200°, on treatment with diazomethane, it was identified as coclaurine⁵.

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Chemical Investigation of *Alysicarpus bupleurifolius* DC

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ALYSICARPUS *bupleurifolius* DC (Leguminosae) is an annual herb¹. In India it occurs widely in the Himalayas ascending North West upto 1200 m in Kumaon. The plant has not been chemically

examined so far. In view of its wide availability in Bundelkhand area and also an important forage legume², its phytochemical investigation was undertaken. Isolation and identification of a mixture of hydrocarbons (C_{27} - C_{34}), aliphatic alcohols (C_{28} - C_{34}), β -sitosterol-D-glucoside, D (+)-pinitol and meso-inositol are reported here. The identity of the compounds was established on the basis of m.m.p. co-tlc, ir and mass spectra and comparison with authentic samples.

Experimental

The plant, collected from the Institute campus during August-September, was found to contain crude protein 11.1%, calcium 1.36% and phosphorus 0.09%. Air dried, powdered aerial part of the plant was exhaustively extracted with ethanol (95%) and the combined extracts were concentrated *in vacuo* and fractionated with hexane-benzene, ethyl acetate and acetone.

Hexane fraction: It was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. Elution with different solvents and their mixtures yielded the following substances.

Hydrocarbons (C_{27} - C_{34}): Elution with hexane afforded a colourless waxy product, m.p. 65-67°. Ir spectrum indicated the presence of long chain n-alkanes³. It was analysed by glc using OV-1 column and temperature programming from 120 to 300° at 2°/min, injection temperature 250°, detector temperature 350°. A tentative carbon number was assigned to each peak on the basis of the retention time of standard alkane (C_{27} - C_{34}) and the use of parafilm⁴. It was also confirmed by field ionisation mass spectrum (fims)⁵.

Alcohols (C_{28} - C_{34}): Further elution with hexane-benzene (4:1) afforded a colourless waxy solid, m.p. 83-84°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 2 920, 2 850, 1 450, 1 375, 1 040, 740 and 720 cm^{-1} . Glc analysis showed it to be a mixture of mainly seven components. The eims showed a series of peaks at odd mass corresponding to $C_nH_{2n+1}^+$, $C_nH_{2n-1}^+$ and $C_nH_{2n+1}O^+$ ions and prominent even mass ion peaks at m/z 392, 406, 420, 434, 448, 462 and 478. These peaks corresponded to the molecular ions of the olefins produced by dehydration of the corresponding alcohols. Hence, the solid was shown to be a mixture of straight chain aliphatic alcohols. The field desorption mass spectrum (fdms)⁴ of the solid confirmed the molecular weights as 410, 424, 438, 452, 466, 480 and 494. It formed an acetate ν_{max} (KBr) 2 900, 2 850, 1 730 ($OCOCH_3$), 1 460, 1 360, 1 240, 740 and 720 cm^{-1} . The fdms of the acetate mixture showed peaks at m/z 452, 466, 480, 494, 508, 522 and 536 which represented the molecular ions of the acetates of the respective alcohols. Thus from the above data, the waxy solid was found to be a mixture of straight chain aliphatic alcohols (C_{28} - C_{34}).

Benzene fraction :

β -Setosterol-D-glucoside, m.p. 300° (MeOH), $[\alpha]_D^{25} -43^\circ$; tetraacetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 166-67°; acid hydrolysis furnished β -sitosterol (m.m.p. and co-tlc) and D-glucose (co-pc). The compound was shown to be identical with β -sitosterol-D-glucoside.

Acetone fraction :

It was chromatographed on silica gel column. Elution with different solvents and their mixture yielded two compounds: D(+)-Pinitol, m.p. 186°, identical (ms and ir) with an authentic specimen, pentacetate, m.p. 98°; and meso-inositol, m.p. 218-219°, identical (ms and ir) with an authentic sample, hexaacetate, m.p. 215°.

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3-(p-Acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazene-N-oxide. A New Reagent for Gravimetric Determination of Nickel(II) and Palladium(II) and their Separation from Binary Mixture

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THE so-called hydroxytriazene has been recently shown from ir spectra to exist predominantly in the tautomeric N-oxide form¹. Such ligands have been used both as analytical reagents and as complex former²⁻⁷. We recommend in this communication a new triazene derivative, 3-(p-acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazene-N-oxide for the gravimetric determination of Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺. The reagent reacts with Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ quantitatively in the pH ranges, 6-10 and 1.5-10, forming deep yellow, Ni(C₁₄H₁₃O₂N₃)₂ and buff coloured, Pd(C₁₄H₁₃O₂N₃)₂ complexes, respectively. The determinations of both the metal ions in the presence of large number of foreign ions and from their binary mixture have been described.

Experimental

3-(p-Acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazene-N-oxide : The reagent was prepared by coupling phenylhydroxylamine suspended in cooled acidified water with diazo salt of p-aminoacetophenone at 0°. The pH of the reaction mixture containing yellow pasty mass was raised around 5 by saturated sodium acetate solution and kept for 1 h. The light yellow compound was recrystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 158° (Found : N, 16.32; C, 65.60; H, 5.22. C₁₄H₁₃O₂N₃ requires : N, 16.47; C, 65.88; H, 5.10%).

Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ solutions : MCl₂ (E. Merck, M= Ni or Pd) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and the metal content was determined gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime⁸.

A Cambridge bench model pH meter was used to record the acidity of the solutions. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

Procedure : Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ (3.0-40 mg) were precipitated from hot solutions (200 ml) using at least 1.5 times the theoretical amounts of reagent in warm ethanol (15 ml) at the pH range 6-10 and 1.5-10 respectively, adjusted by dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The deep yellow Ni²⁺-complex and buff coloured Pd²⁺-complex were digested on boiling water-bath for 30 min and filtered hot through weighed Gooch crucibles no. 4 and 3, respectively, washed with hot water, dried at 110-20° and weighed as M(C₁₄H₁₃O₂N₃)₂. The gravimetric factors for nickel and palladium are 0.1036 and 0.1732, respectively.

The standard deviations for several determinations of Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ (9.0 mg each) were found to be ± 0.28 and $\pm 0.33\%$, respectively.

Separation and determination of Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ present in a binary mixture : Pd²⁺ was first determined from the binary mixture (150-200 ml) at pH 2.0 using reagent 3-4 times of the total metal ions in the usual way. The volume of the filtrate and the washing was then reduced to 200 ml and Ni²⁺ was determined following the procedure described.

Procedure in presence of diverse ions : Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ (9.0mg each) could be determined at pH 7.0 and 3.0, respectively in the presence of the following foreign ions using tartrate (1.0-1.5 g) as masking agent: Al³⁺, Bi³⁺, As³⁺, Ag⁺, Pb²⁺ and Sn²⁺, 30 mg each; Be²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺, MoO₄²⁻, WO₄²⁻, VO₃⁻, ZrO²⁺, HfO²⁺, Nb^v, Ta^v, Rh³⁺, Pt²⁺, Cs²⁺ and TiO²⁺, 50 mg each. However Fe³⁺ (30 mg), Hg²⁺ and Cd²⁺ (50 mg each) and UO₃²⁺ (50 mg) needed ascorbic acid plus phosphoric acid, potassium iodide and ammonium acetate as the masking agents, respectively. Cr³⁺, Mn²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ do not interfere with the determination of Pd but do with Ni estimation. Anions, such as F⁻ (500 mg), SCN⁻ (100 mg), AsO₄²⁻ (100 mg), BO₃⁻ (100 mg), oxalate and citrate (100 mg each) and PO₄²⁻ (200 mg) are tolerable in both the cases. Disodium